

NANO-COMPOSITES: FROM RHEOLOGY TO FORMING PROCESS SIMULATION

F. Chinesta, A. Poitou
EADS Corporate Foundation International Chair
GeM UMR CNRS – Centrale Nantes
1 rue de la Noe, BP 92101, F-44321 Nantes cedex 3, France
Francisco.Chinesta@ec-nantes.fr

E. Cueto
I3A, Universidad de Zaragoza
Maria de Luna 7. E-50012, Spain.
ecueto@unizar.es

M. Macley
Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Cambridge,
Pembroke Street, CB2 3RA, United Kingdom
mrm5@cam.ac.uk

SUMMARY

This paper is concerned with the rheological modeling of untreated Carbon Nanotubes (CNTs) suspended within an epoxy resin and its application in nanocomposites forming processes. A new model named the “Aggregation/Orientation” (AO) model was developed to describe the experimental findings. However, it predicts an “affine” orientation of the tubes with the fluid deformation that is not observed experimentally. In this work we propose an alternative rheological model that is then employed for simulating film processing by employing spin coating.

Keywords: Carbon nanotubes; Rheology; Orientation/Aggregation model; Spin coating

INTRODUCTION

In terms of modelling, the evolution of flow curves for CNT suspensions can be described by different empirical models such as the Cross model, the Carreau model and the Krieger-Dougherty model. A stress-microstructure model, however, is desirable as information such as CNT orientation and state of aggregation is intimately related to the final physical properties of CNT composite materials. The current CNT modelling is based on both fibre orientation models and transient network modelling concepts.

In some of our former works we proposed an orientation based model for describing the rheology of functionalized CNT (Ma *et al.*, 2009). That orientation based model was

applied for simulating spin coating processes involving semi-dilute suspensions of functionalized CNTs (Cueto *et al.*, 2008). However, this model was not able to describe the rheological behaviour of non-functionalized CNT suspensions. In that case an orientation/aggregation based model was proposed to take into account the presence and evolution of aggregates whose impact on the suspension rheology is significant (see Ma *et al.*, 2008). However, the orientation/aggregation model proposed in Ma *et al.* (2008) has some weakness because the tube orientation was assumed governed by the Jeffery equation that assuming the aspect ratio of tubes predicts a quasi-affine orientation of tubes with the matrix fluid deformation. This prediction seems to be in contradiction with some experimental observations that indicate that tubes belonging to large aggregates don't orient as the Jeffery's model predicts.

The first part of the work revisits the orientation/aggregation model proposed in Ma *et al.* (2008). Then, the question related to the delayed orientation is addressed. A two populations model similar to the one considered for modelling associative polymers (Hernandez Cifre *et al.*, 2003 and Vaccaro and Marucci, 2000) is then developed. In that model the orientation velocity is different for both populations. Finally the model is applied for simulating spin coating.

RHEOLOGICAL MODELING

The orientation model

In the context of short-fibre suspensions modelling, an orientation model can be used to describe the evolution of steady shear viscosity by coupling the flow kinematics with fibre orientation. First, an orientation model was assumed where the CNTs were considered as short, rigid fibres that can rotate and align in a shear flow and where the evolution of the viscosity contribution due to the presence of CNTs depended only on the orientation of CNTs.

The momentum balance equation (neglecting the inertia and mass terms):

$$\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{0} \quad (1)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the stress tensor. The mass balance equation for an incompressible fluid reads:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} = 0 \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{v} represents the velocity field.

The constitutive equation for a dilute suspension of high aspect-ratio particles (with negligible Brownian diffusion) can be written as:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = -P\mathbf{I} + 2\eta(\mathbf{D} + N_p(\mathbf{a}_4 : \mathbf{D})) \quad (3)$$

where P denotes the hydrostatic pressure, \mathbf{I} is the unit tensor, η is the matrix viscosity, \mathbf{D} is the strain-rate tensor, N_p is a scalar parameter that depends on fiber concentration and aspect ratio, ":" is the tensor product twice contracted (i.e. $(\mathbf{a}_4 : \mathbf{D})_{ij} = (\mathbf{a}_4)_{ijkl} \mathbf{D}_{kl}$) and \mathbf{a}_4 is the fourth order orientation tensor and it is defined as:

$$\mathbf{a}_4 = \int \mathbf{p} \otimes \mathbf{p} \otimes \mathbf{p} \otimes \mathbf{p} \psi(\mathbf{p}) d\mathbf{p} \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{p} is the unit vector aligned in the fiber axis direction, " \otimes " denotes the tensorial product (i.e. $(\mathbf{p} \otimes \mathbf{p})_{ij} = p_i p_j$), and $\psi(\mathbf{p})$ is the orientation distribution function which satisfies the normality condition $\int \psi(\mathbf{p}) d\mathbf{p} = 1$. In general, the distribution function depends on the physical coordinates \mathbf{x} , the time t and the conformation coordinates \mathbf{p} (i.e. $\psi(\mathbf{x}, t, \mathbf{p})$), but if the flow is homogeneous and steady, the fibre orientation distribution would only depend on the conformation coordinates, (i.e. $\psi(\mathbf{p})$). For dilute and non-aggregating short fibre suspensions, different analytical expressions for the parameter N_p are available (Petrie, 1999). However, those expressions do not immediately apply to semi-dilute/concentrated or aggregating suspensions. Aggregation has been observed within the semi-dilute untreated CNT suspensions studied in this paper and N_p is therefore determined from experimental data fitting.

If all the fibres are completely aligned in the direction the fourth order orientation tensor can be written in the following form:

$$\mathbf{a}_4 = \mathbf{a}_2 \otimes \mathbf{a}_2 \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{a}_2 = \int \mathbf{p} \otimes \mathbf{p} \psi(\mathbf{p}) d\mathbf{p}$ denotes the second order orientation tensor and corresponding components are given as $(\mathbf{a}_4)_{ijkl} = (\mathbf{a}_2)_{ij} (\mathbf{a}_2)_{kl}$.

In cases where the fibres are not completely aligned in one direction, Eq. (5) is not exact, but it provides an approximation for the fourth-order orientation tensor. Equation (5) is also known as the quadratic closure relation: $\mathbf{a}_4^{quad} = \mathbf{a}_2 \otimes \mathbf{a}_2$ and other forms of closure relations are also available in the literature (see for example Advani and Tucker (1990) and Dupret *et al.*, (1998)).

The orientation distribution function $\psi(\mathbf{p})$ can be determined by solving its balance equation, which is also known as the Fokker-Planck equation:

$$\frac{d\psi(\mathbf{p})}{dt} + \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{p}} \left(\psi(\mathbf{p}) \frac{d\mathbf{p}}{dt} \right) = 0 \quad (6)$$

where $\frac{d\psi}{dt}$ is the material derivative: $\frac{d\psi}{dt} = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \psi$. Once the distribution function is calculated, the computation of its moments (orientation tensors) then becomes straightforward and does not require any closure approximation.

For a dilute suspension of spheroids and in the absence of Brownian motion, the evolution of fibre orientation was described by Jeffery (1922):

$$\frac{d\mathbf{p}}{dt} = \boldsymbol{\Omega} \cdot \mathbf{p} + \lambda \left(\mathbf{D} \cdot \mathbf{p} - (\mathbf{p}^T \cdot \mathbf{D} \cdot \mathbf{p}) \mathbf{p} \right) \quad (7)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\Omega}$ is the vorticity tensor and λ is a constant that depends on the fibre aspect ratio r ($r = \text{fiber length} / \text{fibre diameter}$):

$$\lambda = (r^2 - 1) / (r^2 + 1) \quad (8)$$

For particles with an infinite aspect ratio $\lambda \approx 1$, Eq. (7) reduces to:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{p}}{dt} = \nabla \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{p} - (\mathbf{p}^T \cdot \mathbf{D} \cdot \mathbf{p}) \mathbf{p} \quad (9)$$

By introducing Eq. (7) into the expression defining the second order orientation tensor, the equation governing the evolution of the second order orientation tensor can be deduced:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{a}_2}{dt} = \boldsymbol{\Omega} \cdot \mathbf{a}_2 - \mathbf{a}_2 \cdot \boldsymbol{\Omega} + \lambda (\mathbf{D} \cdot \mathbf{a}_2 + \mathbf{a}_2 \cdot \mathbf{D} - 2(\mathbf{a}_4 : \mathbf{D})) \quad (10)$$

In the case of semi-dilute fibre suspensions, Folgar and Tucker (1984) proposed the introduction of a diffusion term (D_r) in Eq. (6) to account for fiber interaction effects, resulting in the following expression:

$$\frac{d\psi(\mathbf{p})}{dt} + \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{p}} \left\{ \psi(\mathbf{p}) \frac{d\mathbf{p}}{dt} \right\} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{p}} \left\{ D_r \frac{\partial \psi(\mathbf{p})}{\partial \mathbf{p}} \right\} \quad (11)$$

The equation governing the evolution of \mathbf{a}_2 (in 3-D) then becomes:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{a}_2}{dt} = \boldsymbol{\Omega} \cdot \mathbf{a}_2 - \mathbf{a}_2 \cdot \boldsymbol{\Omega} + k (\mathbf{D} \cdot \mathbf{a}_2 + \mathbf{a}_2 \cdot \mathbf{D} - 2(\mathbf{a}_4 : \mathbf{D})) - 6D_r \left(\mathbf{a}_2 - \frac{\mathbf{I}}{3} \right) \quad (12)$$

Eq. (12) shows that the evolution equation for the second-order orientation tensor involves the fourth-order orientation tensor and in order to solve the problem in a closed form, closure approximations which express the fourth-order orientation tensor in terms of lower-order tensors are commonly used (Advani and Tucker, 1990; Dupret and Verleye, 1999). Instead of using closure approximations, a number of authors solved the Fokker-Planck description directly (see for example Ammar *et al.*, 2006). However, the latter approach also requires the computation of a multi-dimensional distribution function and thus involves considerable computation efforts.

In the Fokker-Planck based orientation model, N_p and D_r are the key adjustable parameters to fit with experimental data. The model was found to be successful in capturing the shear thinning characteristic for some surface-treated CNT suspensions (Ma *et al.*, 2009), where no optically resolvable CNT aggregate was observed. The success of this model for treated CNTs can be understood in terms of the non-aggregating characteristic of treated CNT suspensions, where CNT orientation was expected to be the key factor in controlling the evolution of steady shear viscosity.

The Fokker-Planck based orientation model with the use of a single D_r and N_p values, however, failed to fit the experimental flow curves for untreated CNT suspensions, where the viscosity enhancement was very pronounced at low shear rates. It is believed that the extra contribution to shear viscosity at low shear rates is due to the presence of CNT aggregates, which were experimentally observed in optical microstructure studies.

The Orientation/Aggregation model

The FP orientation model was unable to describe the shear-thinning characteristic for untreated CNT suspensions, and therefore, a new model named the Aggregation/Orientation (AO) model was developed. The new model considered a hierarchy of CNT aggregate structures within an untreated CNT suspension, where the

shear viscosity was controlled by the state of aggregation and CNT orientation. The Fokker-Planck description was modified to incorporate aggregation/disaggregation kinetics and the derivation of the AO model is summarized in this section.

The aggregation/orientation distribution function in the AO model is written as $\psi(\mathbf{x}, t, \mathbf{p}, n)$, where $n \in [0, 1]$ describes the state of aggregation ($n = 0$ corresponds to CNTs that are free from entanglement and $n = 1$ represents a CNT aggregate network). It is assumed that the flow is steady and homogeneous and that different populations (n) are present within the control volume considered in the balance equation.

For an arbitrary population n (where $n \neq 0$ nor 1), the population can increase as a result of the aggregation of smaller aggregates ($r < n$) or the disaggregation of larger aggregates ($r > n$). On the other hand, the population n can decrease because of the disaggregation of population n forming less entangled aggregates ($r < n$) or the aggregation of n forming more entangled aggregates ($r > n$). If a constant aggregation velocity (v_c) and a constant disaggregation velocity of (v_d) are assumed, the following balance expression can be written for the population n :

$$\left. \frac{\partial \psi(\mathbf{p}, n)}{\partial t} \right|_{\text{Aggregation}} dn d\mathbf{p} dt = \left\{ v_c \int_{r=0}^{r=n} \psi(\mathbf{p}, r) dr + v_d \int_{r=n}^{r=1} \psi(\mathbf{p}, r) dr - v_d \psi(\mathbf{p}, n) \int_{r=0}^{r=n} dr - v_c \psi(\mathbf{p}, n) \int_{r=n}^{r=1} dr \right\} dn d\mathbf{p} dt \quad (13)$$

The balance equation considering orientation only is given as:

$$\left. \frac{\partial \psi(\mathbf{p}, n)}{\partial t} \right|_{\text{Orientation}} dn d\mathbf{p} dt = \left\{ -\frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{p}} \left\{ \psi(\mathbf{p}, n) \frac{d\mathbf{p}}{dt} \right\} + \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{p}} \left\{ D_r(n) \frac{\partial \psi(\mathbf{p}, n)}{\partial \mathbf{p}} \right\} \right\} dn d\mathbf{p} dt \quad (14)$$

The Fokker-Planck equation which includes both CNT orientation and aggregation/disaggregation kinetics becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \psi(\mathbf{p}, n)}{\partial t} &= \left. \frac{\partial \psi(\mathbf{p}, n)}{\partial t} \right|_{\text{Orientation}} + \left. \frac{\partial \psi(\mathbf{p}, n)}{\partial t} \right|_{\text{Aggregation}} \\ &= \left\{ -\frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{p}} \left\{ \psi(\mathbf{p}, n) \frac{\partial \mathbf{p}}{\partial t} \right\} + \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{p}} \left\{ D_r(n) \frac{\partial \psi(\mathbf{p}, n)}{\partial t} \right\} \right\} \\ &+ \left\{ v_c \int_{r=0}^{r=n} \psi(\mathbf{p}, r) dr + v_d \int_{r=n}^{r=1} \psi(\mathbf{p}, r) dr - v_d \psi(\mathbf{p}, n) \int_{r=0}^{r=n} dr - v_c \psi(\mathbf{p}, n) \int_{r=n}^{r=1} dr \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

For a homogenous flow at steady state,

$$\begin{aligned} &\left\{ -\frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{p}} \left\{ \psi(\mathbf{p}, n) \frac{d\mathbf{p}}{dt} \right\} + \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{p}} \left\{ D_r(n) \frac{\partial \psi(\mathbf{p}, n)}{\partial \mathbf{p}} \right\} \right\} + \\ &+ \left\{ v_c \int_{r=0}^{r=n} \psi(\mathbf{p}, r) dr + v_d \int_{r=n}^{r=1} \psi(\mathbf{p}, r) dr - v_d \psi(\mathbf{p}, n) \int_{r=0}^{r=n} dr - v_c \psi(\mathbf{p}, n) \int_{r=n}^{r=1} dr \right\} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

The solution of Eq. (16) should verify the normality condition $\int_{S(0,1)} \int_0^1 \psi(\mathbf{p}, n) dn d\mathbf{p} = 1$, where $S(0,1)$ represents the unit sphere surface centered at the origin of the orientation conformation space.

The distribution function $\psi(\mathbf{p}, n)$ can be obtained by solving Eq. (16) and the fourth order orientation tensor can be expressed as:

$$\mathbf{a}_4(n) = \int \mathbf{p} \otimes \mathbf{p} \otimes \mathbf{p} \otimes \mathbf{p} \psi(\mathbf{p}, n) d\mathbf{p} \quad (17)$$

The stress contribution due to the presence of CNTs for a multi-population system can be obtained by generalizing Eq. (3)

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = 2\eta \int_0^1 N_p(n) (\mathbf{a}_4(n) : \mathbf{D}) dn \quad (18)$$

The rheological model described above provides a first approximation for describing a suspension with aggregating CNTs and contains four parameters: the concentration and aspect-ratio parameter N_p , the rotary diffusion coefficient (D_r) and the aggregation and disaggregation velocities (v_c and v_d).

This model was successfully applied for describing the non-linear rheological behavior of non-functionalized CNTs suspensions. The model only involves 4 rheological parameters easily identified by fitting the experimental flow curves. However, its use in forming processes simulation, where complex flows geometries are encountered, remains quite delicate because the significant computing time cost associated to the solution of the transient orientation/aggregation kinetic theory model.

On the other hand, and from a conceptual point of view, we must accept that fact of assuming high values of the diffusion coefficient for nanotubes belonging to large aggregates does not have any physical foundation. Simply, as we know that the diffusion coefficient tends to induce an isotropic tube distribution and according to the observations (Hobbie and Fry, 2006; Ma *et al.*, 2007) this is the orientation state observed in aggregates, we decided to increase artificially the diffusion coefficient to be able to predict the observed state of the microstructure.

DELAYING ORIENTATION

In this section we are trying to propose a mechanism that could explain the lower observed order parameter related to aggregates.

For this purpose we start given a physical interpretation of the Jeffery equation. We consider the case of a rigid tube, with negligible mass and with a quasi infinite aspect ratio, immersed in a Newtonian fluid flow characterized by the velocity field that is assumed non perturbed by the presence of the tube. The dimension of the tube being micrometric, the shear rate can be assumed constant in the scale of the tube. The length of the tube is $2L$, the origin of the system of coordinates is assumed located on the tube centre of gravity and the tube orientation is defined by a unit vector \mathbf{p} aligned with the tube axis. The tube is idealized by using two dumbbells located at the tube ends and on

which the different forces apply, joined by rigid connector of length $2L$ (see the schema in figure 1).

Figure 1. Schema of a tube suspended within a flow.

We are assuming that the tube is subjected to hydrodynamic drag forces \mathbf{F}_H , being Brownian forces ignored by the moment. The hydrodynamic forces write:

$$\mathbf{F}_H = \xi(\mathbf{v} - L\dot{\mathbf{p}}) \quad (19)$$

where \mathbf{v} is the fluid velocity at the position occupied by the dumbbell (as just commented this velocity is assumed undisturbed by the presence of the tube) and $L\dot{\mathbf{p}}$ represents the velocity of the dumbbell. Thus, Eq. (19) can be rewritten as:

$$\mathbf{F}_H = \xi L(\nabla\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{p} - \dot{\mathbf{p}}) \quad (20)$$

The equilibrium of torques allows to the Jeffery equation

$$\dot{\mathbf{p}} = \nabla\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{p} - (\mathbf{p} \cdot \nabla\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{p})\mathbf{p} \quad (21)$$

For introducing a delay in the tube orientation with respect to the fluid deformation we decided pragmatically to introduce an additional force that scales with the dumbbell velocity and tends to resist its movement. This force that we denote by \mathbf{F}_R , writes:

$$\mathbf{F}_R = -\beta L(\dot{\mathbf{p}} - \boldsymbol{\Omega} \cdot \mathbf{p}) \quad (22)$$

that allows to

$$\dot{\mathbf{p}} = (\boldsymbol{\Omega} \cdot \mathbf{p} + \kappa(\mathbf{D} \cdot \mathbf{p} - (\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{D} \cdot \mathbf{p})\mathbf{p})) \quad (23)$$

that corresponds to the usual Jeffery's equation where the ellipsoid shape factor results

$$\lambda = \kappa = \frac{\xi}{\xi + \beta}.$$

If the reaction coefficient β in Eq. (22) is large enough $\kappa \approx 0$ implying $\dot{\mathbf{p}} = \boldsymbol{\Omega} \cdot \mathbf{p}$, that is, tubes rotate according to the flow vorticity, and then the order parameter remains unchanged (the microstructure is rotating but the magnitude of the orientation remains unchanged).

Thus, if we come back to the orientation/aggregation model described in the previous section, more than increasing artificially the diffusion coefficient to resist the orientation induced by the Jeffery's kinematics related to infinite aspect ratio tubes, one

could simply consider that in the Jeffery's equation the ellipsoids factor evolves in a way allowing tubes in aggregates to have $\lambda=0$ allowing the rotation of the microstructure without modifying the order parameter that characterizes the magnitude of the orientation. We propose a model in this direction in the next section.

A TWO POPULATIONS MODEL

In this section we introduce a model that consists of two populations of tubes inspired of models proposed for associative polymers (Hernandez Cifre *et al.*, 2003; Vaccaro and Marucci, 2000). One related to the entangled tubes constituting the aggregates, and the other one that concerns isolated tubes that can freely align according to the Jeffery's equation for particles with infinite aspect ratio. In what follows, we assume a homogeneous system whose microstructure does not depend on the physical space.

The distribution functions related to these two populations are denoted by $\Xi(\mathbf{p})$ and $\Gamma(\mathbf{p})$ for entangled and free tubes respectively. The Fokker-Planck equations related to both populations write:

$$\begin{cases} \left\{ \frac{d\Xi(\mathbf{p})}{dt} + \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{p}} \left\{ \Xi(\mathbf{p}) \frac{d\mathbf{p}}{dt} \Big|_A \right\} - \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{p}} \left\{ D_r \frac{\partial \Xi(\mathbf{p})}{\partial \mathbf{p}} \right\} \right\} = v_c \Gamma(\mathbf{p}) - v_d \Xi(\mathbf{p}) \\ \left\{ \frac{d\Gamma(\mathbf{p})}{dt} + \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{p}} \left\{ \Gamma(\mathbf{p}) \frac{d\mathbf{p}}{dt} \Big|_F \right\} - \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{p}} \left\{ D_r \frac{\partial \Gamma(\mathbf{p})}{\partial \mathbf{p}} \right\} \right\} = -v_c \Gamma(\mathbf{p}) + v_d \Xi(\mathbf{p}) \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

where the rotary velocities read:

$$\begin{cases} \left. \frac{d\mathbf{p}}{dt} \right|_A = \boldsymbol{\Omega} \cdot \mathbf{p} \\ \left. \frac{d\mathbf{p}}{dt} \right|_F = \nabla \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{p} - (\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{D} \cdot \mathbf{p}) \mathbf{p} \end{cases} \quad (25)$$

Now, the extra-stress tensor related to the presence of tubes writes:

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = 2\eta \left((N_p)_A \left({}^A \mathbf{a}_4 : \mathbf{D} \right) + (N_p)_F \left({}^F \mathbf{a}_4 : \mathbf{D} \right) \right) \quad (26)$$

where $(N_p)_A$ and $(N_p)_F$ are two rheological parameters related to the contribution of aggregates and free tubes to the stress respectively. The two fourth order orientation tensors in Eq. (45) are given by:

$$\begin{cases} {}^A \mathbf{a}_4 = \int_{S^{(0,1)}} \mathbf{p} \otimes \mathbf{p} \otimes \mathbf{p} \otimes \mathbf{p} \Xi(\mathbf{p}) d\mathbf{p} \\ {}^F \mathbf{a}_4 = \int_{S^{(0,1)}} \mathbf{p} \otimes \mathbf{p} \otimes \mathbf{p} \otimes \mathbf{p} \Gamma(\mathbf{p}) d\mathbf{p} \end{cases} \quad (27)$$

SIMULATING SPIN COATING PROCESSES

In this section we are simulating spin coating processes. For this purpose we are coupling the flow kinematics with the macroscopic modelling just described involving two populations and the evolution of the associated orientation tensors.

The numerical technique employed for solving the momentum balance equations is the Natural Element Method (NEM), deeply described in Gonzalez et al. (2007). In Cueto et al. (2008), we described the application of such a technique for simulating the free surface problem related to spin coating processes.

In what follows we are considering the case in which the aggregation velocity is much lower than the disaggregation. The before presented model was applied to the simulation of spinning a drop of CNT suspension, with the assumption that the initial shape is Gaussian. The model was composed of 977 nodes under axisymmetric assumptions for the flow (but not for the orientation field, which is three-dimensional). Non-slip boundary conditions were assumed at the horizontal plane, whereas symmetry boundary conditions are assumed at the axis of symmetry.

If we consider that the disaggregation velocity is always dominant over the aggregation one, the resulting behaviour of the fluid will be essentially the same described in Cueto et al. (2008). Here we consider the orientation as governed by a factor $\lambda = 1$. The results concerning the CNTs orientation are shown in Fig. 2. It can be noticed how the CNTs tend to rapidly align with the flow. To understand the apparent isotropic final distribution of the CNTs it must be noticed that the orientation tensor is fully three-dimensional, and that CNTs tend to orient with the divergent flow field, and thus in the r - θ plane. That is why the ellipses are of considerable lower radius than those at initial time steps.

Figure 2. Orientation field in the r - θ plane. Time steps 1, 10 and 30. $\Delta t = 0.01$ s., $\lambda = 1$.

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